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Hands-on work in a web-based Basic Electronics course

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ABSTRACT

For the past eighteen years, LUT university has offered a basic electronics course for secondary high-school students as an open and distance education. Over the years, the course has evolved in many ways. As the latest development step, a set of practical hands-on activities was added to the mainly web-based course in the quest to make the study matters more interesting and better relate the theory of electronics to the everyday life.

The latest edition of the course consisted of self-study materials, weekly assignments on a learning platform, a laboratory day on the university's premises, and an electronics-related project work, where students devised a project plan, executed, documented, and presented the project. To get acquainted with the Arduino platform the students completed three small programming exercises.

There were many different challenges in adding hands-on work to a distance teaching course. The students came from seventeen different high schools, hundreds of kilometres apart, and most of them quite far from the university. Most of the students had no prior experience in using Arduino boards, and the high-school teachers were not involved with the course, so all the supervision had to be arranged by the university.

Despite the obstacles, the addition of a hands-on element to the course was considered a success. In the course feedback, the students rated the project work high

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in terms of its support for learning. In the web discussions, many of the students mentioned the project as the most interesting experience in the course.

1 INTRODUCTION

Web-based teaching offers new kinds of opportunities in many areas of engineering education, including outreach activities. In outreach activities, the benefits of online education are much the same as in degree education: flexibility in time and space makes the course accessible to those for whom it would otherwise not be possible to participate in the course. Web-based learning platforms also allow new types of teaching and learning tasks and new means of feedback and assessment [1].

Although web-based activities may enable reaching wider audiences, in order to be considered successful outreach activities, they also have to be interesting enough for people to engage in them and complete them. Student persistence in a web-based course can be enhanced in many ways, such as continuous facilitation by the teacher [2] or built-in time management help for the learners [3]. However, at least in engineering-related outreach activities, hands-on experiences have been noted to increase participants' knowledge, interest, and confidence in the field [4].

The challenge of combining web-based and hands-on activities had been tackled in the Basic Electronics course for high-school students for years by organizing a web-based course ending with a day at the laboratory. This arrangement followed the traditional “theory first” approach and was based on the idea that on the laboratory day the students could put into practice the things that they had learned before. It did not, however, ideally support experiential learning through interplay of theory and practice [5], and thus, some novel additional features had to be developed.

2 BASIC ELECTRONICS FOR HIGH-SCHOOL STUDENTS

Basic Electronics is a 5 ECTS, Bachelor-level study module, which is compulsory for students in the degree programme of Electrical Engineering. For the past eighteen years it has also been offered to the secondary high-school students as an open and distance education. The intended learning outcomes for the module state that after the module students will be able to:

- “recognize the most important passive and active components in electronics and list their applications,
- explain the main differences between analog and digital electronics,
- define concepts of amplification on filtering,
- explain the operation and simplified physical structure of an ideal semiconductor diode,
- describe the operation and main applications of a transistor,
- describe the operation principle of digital logic gate and list common logic functions,
- recognize the main phases and materials of manufacturing an electrical apparatus,
- apply Ohm's law, Kirchhoff's voltage and current laws, and definition of electrical power to a simple electrical circuit, and
- recognize the main components of an embedded system” [6].

Before the year 2018, the module consisted of a seven weeks long self-study period, where a new topic was introduced every week. Topics of the course were: Introduction to electronics and signals, Passive components and filtering, Amplification in electronics, Semiconductor materials and diodes, Transistors, Digital electronics, and Manufacturing techniques in electronics. After studying each topic, the students took a week test, and after completing all the topics, they took an exam on the learning platform.

The self-study materials were accompanied by weekly discussion forums, where students could ask questions and make comments. Active participation in the discussions could yield some extra points to be added to the week test and exam points. The course area also included forums for more general discussion about the course.

After passing the exam, the students could attend a laboratory day at the campus, where they learned soldering by building an electronic circuit from an assembly kit, such as a blinking LED array in the form of a heart. Furthermore, the students could practice their presentation skills by explaining the operating principles of their circuits to their peers.

In recent years, the number of high-school students enrolling in the module has varied between 50 and 70. The drop-out rate is quite high, which is common in web-based courses and trainings. Typically, about half of the enrolled students also finish the module and get a grade. Students come from about fifteen different high schools in a large geographical region. The students may live as far as 200 km from the university campus. Some attendees may be the only ones from their high school, whereas some schools get more than ten of their students to enroll in the course.

3 PROJECT WORK WITH THE ARDUINO ELECTRONICS PLATFORM

In spring 2018, a project work was added to the module to enhance the students' hands-on learning experience. The decision to include more practical elements in the course was based on the good student feedback regarding the laboratory day, the positive experiences of introducing the open-source electronics platform Arduino [7] in other outreach activities [8], and the development ideas collected from high-school teachers and headmasters in the region.

The concept of project work was first tested with electrical engineering B.Sc. students. The theme of the project was decided to be kept open so that the students could make a small application according to their own interest. The students were free to choose their project topic; however, it had to apply a microcontroller platform, in this case Arduino. Furthermore, the project had to have an interface to the outside world, such as a button, a sensor, or a LED display. A couple of different project examples were built and documented to illustrate the diverse options available. The students were also given a list of components at their disposal, but they were also told where they could easily purchase additional components if required.

The project work was divided into four subtasks: writing a project plan, building the gadget, making a project report, and peer evaluation of the works of the others. Three small assignments were devised to familiarize the students with Arduino boards. The timetable of the self-study and the project work is presented in *Table 1*. The projects were done mainly in groups of 2–4 students, but also an individual project was an option chosen by some.

Table 1. Timetable of the learning activities

Week	Self-study	Project work
6	Getting to know the course and the course mates	
7	Introduction to electronics and signals	
8	Passive components and filtering	Project info
9		
10	Amplification in electronics	Forming of project groups
11	Semiconductor materials and diodes,	Arduino assignment I
12	Transistors	Arduino assignment II
13		Arduino assignment III Handing in the project plan
14	Digital electronics	Working on the project
15	Manufacturing techniques in electronics	Working on the project
16		Working on the project
17	Web-exam	Working on the project
18		Handing in the project report
19		Peer review of project reports
20	Laboratory visit to LUT University	

A designated discussion forum was established for the supervision and guidance of the project work. The work was mainly guided by two teaching assistants, who for example reminded the students of the approaching deadlines or informed them about different instructions and guiding materials. Some students were very active in answering other students' questions and gave the others good tips and advice.

In addition to the topic of the project, the students could choose their mode of documentation. Again, a couple of different alternatives were offered. Most of the documentations contained images or videos or other kind of multimedia elements, which added also to the objective to make the learning more hands-on as opposed to writing plain text only. Students experimented different publication platforms and presentation programs, producing visually and informatively high-quality reports. Further, the oral presentation of the projects during the laboratory day enhanced the students' generic communication skills, team building, interpersonal skills, and the sense of responsibility—skills required of modern electrical engineers [9] as well as many other professionals.

4 EFFECTS ON LEARNING

In general, the implementation of the practical project work in the otherwise web-based course succeeded as planned. The basic figures of the year 2017 (before the project work) and year 2018 (first implementation of the project work) are collected in *Table 2* and show improvement in all the areas: the proportions of students completing the exam and the whole module, and the average grade of the students both in the exam and for the whole module are higher. It should be noted that the grading scheme for the module varied between the years, because in 2018 the Arduino assignments and project accounted for 30% of the total grade.

Table 2. Key figures of the Basic Electronics course for high-school students

	2017	2018
Enrolled students	61	70
Students completing the web exam	31	45
Students completing the whole module	30	41
Average grade in the web exam (max. 5)	3.43	3.59
Standard deviation of the exam grade	0.50	0.49
Average grade for the module (max. 5)	3.1	3.8

The web exam was exactly the same in both years; the relative distribution of the exam grades is illustrated in *Fig. 1*. Even though the number of students taking the web exam in 2018 was almost 50% higher than in 2017, the average, median, and mode of the grades were all higher in 2018.

Fig. 1. Distribution of exam grades in the Basic Electronics course for high-school students

At the end of the course, the students were asked to assess their learning experience and the role of different learning activities in it. The survey shows that students perceive the hands-on activities also educative and not just entertaining. The results are collected in *Table 3*.

Table 3. Student feedback regarding the support of different activities for learning

How did the following things support your learning during the course (1=not at all, 4=very much)?	2017 (N=27)	2018 (N=40)
Written teaching material	3.5	3.3
Teaching videos	2.0	2.1
Weekly assignments/quizzes	3.3	3.1
Discussions in the discussion forum	1.7	1.9
Moodle exam	3.0	2.8
Arduino assignments		3.2
Arduino project		3.3
Laboratory work	3.4	3.4
Poster presentation in the laboratory day	2.7	

Students liking the project work also participated in a discussion thread spontaneously started by a student who wanted to know what the others thought of the course. In the thread, the project work got most of the votes as the most interesting thing:

“Absolutely best thing was building with Arduino”

“In my opinion, the best part of the course was the Arduino project, which went really nicely with familiar people, once we got over the starting difficulties.”

In the same discussion thread many students acknowledged the challenges with self-study:

“For me independent studying has been challenging, because I haven’t been able to push myself to study as much as I should have.”

“The course was more difficult for me than they usually are. This may be because of the self-study.”

Some students suspected that they would have learnt better in a more traditional classroom setting:

“I still think that I could have done better if the course had been organized in a more traditional way in the classroom.”

Thus, it seems that adding a hands-on group project in a web-based course in Basic Electronics has the potential to increase students’ interest, support their learning, and bring about better sense of communality to the otherwise quite challenging realm of self-study.

5 CHALLENGES AND DEVELOPMENT NEEDS

Perhaps somewhat surprisingly, some of the major challenges with the implementation of the project work were related to the physical delivery of the microcontrollers and components to the students. Within the rather tight course schedule, the deliveries lost in the mail or in schools delayed the projects of some students and caused confusion and irritation. Unfortunately, some of these problems repeated also in spring 2019, and therefore, a satisfactory logistic solution is yet to be found.

Even though many of the students had never worked with the Arduino platform before, they managed well with the help of our instructions, peer support, and the Internet. Discussion forums in the learning platform seem to work sufficiently once the students

find them, but more help is needed to help the students to navigate in the learning platform and the material bank. Although the high-school students are “digital natives” in many respects, they are not as used to the learning platforms and independent study as the university students and need more orientation and scaffolding for time management and navigation in the course area. In this, the constant web presence of the teacher and teaching assistants along with reminders of different obligations and deadlines is essential.

6 CONCLUSION

Complementing web-based learning with hands-on activities requires some effort but appears to be worth it. Although this kind of a tinkering project in groups adds to the workload of the students and poses some logistic and instructional challenges to the teachers, it also strengthens the connections between theory and practice, lets students use their creativity, enhances the development of generic skills, and increases the peer support and sense of community. As the project undoubtedly increases the students’ time management challenges, it is important to design and structure the activities in a way that scaffolds the student progress, but also to ensure the constant web presence of teaching staff in the course. At its best, combining modern information and communication technology in its different forms and the practical hands-on construction of artefacts in the same outreach activity clearly demonstrates to the high-school students what engineering is all about: creating technological constructs with people and for people.

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